

VISUAL LEARNING STYLE AND ITS BENEFICIAL SIDES

Shovqieva Shohida Bobosher Kizi

Uzbek State Institute of Arts and Culture

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6628389>

Visual Learning Style. We as humans possess the power to remember those which we have caught visually in our memory and that too for a longer period of time. We always remember when teachers used to bring some visually appealing materials to demonstrate in class. Interestingly, visual learner characteristics have proved that knowledge and skill imparted by the help of visually-stimulating materials lasts in our memories for a long time. Therefore, visual learning has proved as an important and effective process.

Referring to another example, if you have lost your keys at home and you have a tendency to close your eyes and imagine the location of your keys, this trick works miraculously. Among various types of learning styles, this process always works for remembering things. This is how we realize the effect of visual images to remember things faster in our day-to-day lives.

Visual learning is one of the best types of learning styles that helps you to see the information to learn it. It captures the image of what it sees, based on spatial awareness, images, colour, brightness, or any other visual information. Therefore, the classroom is the best place for students to learn visually. Nowadays teachers adapt visual methods for teaching by using whiteboards, handouts, images, videos, presentations, etc for effective learning. Visual learners can boost their confidence and performance in school.

Visual learning strategies are being used more across the country. They can help you achieve and manage learning objectives. It helps you to think critically and develop skills such as problem-solving, decision making and better understanding. You can take up many activities for learning such as drawing, writing reports, games, flashcards, displays, photographs, posters, documentaries, OHP sheets, etc.

Benefits of Visual Learning . Visual content plays a very important part of human life. Visual learners account for around 65% of the population. Much research has been conducted to prove the effectiveness of visual learning. It is more appealing than hearing. Visual learners respond to information faster compared to textual information. Here, we will discuss why visual learning is so beneficial for learning.

Effective Strategies of Visual Learning. Visual learning is one of the effective types of learning styles for students. It focuses on learning through reading and watching rather than listening. There are different ways to learn through visuals

such as images, videos, different colour themes, charts, maps, etc. You must understand what are the things required to see, understand and remember the information. Here are some strategies that can help you in better visual learning practice. If you are a visual learner, you imagine things to remember any information. When teachers show you some kind of visual, the information is retained in your mind. As a student, it will help you perform well in your academics. You can integrate the strategies mentioned below for better learning outcomes.

1. Use colour codes for notes, words, textbooks, etc. It will help in retaining the information in your mind
2. Read images, diagrams, pictures, and maps to help you retain the concept in your mind for long periods of time
3. Prepare notes using different colour pens. It helps you to identify the topics easily.
4. Highlight the points, headings, and subheadings to organize notes.
5. Watch informative videos for a better understanding of the subject and quick learning
6. Organize the information that you want to learn in graphs, charts and tables. Excel sheets can help you in drawing charts and creating tables for a better understanding of the information.
7. Draw mind maps for the topics you want to remember for a long time

Visuals help learners grasp concepts easily by stimulating imagination and affecting their cognitive capabilities. Besides, the visual language is also known to have the potential to stretch 'human bandwidth' – which comprises absorbing, comprehending and analysing new information. For example, the infographic below represents how we are pre-wired to automatically interpret relationships between objects which ensures instant comprehension with almost zero effort.

Conclusion. Visual learning isn't an intellectual shortcut for the creator or the learner. You still have to put thought into what you are creating and how it will be received. Apply graphic design concepts to visual learning elements and you will improve the effectiveness of your training.

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